

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: ADU-TWUMWAAH****FIRST NAME: DEBORAH****PROGRAM CODE : DILT****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: Dr. KABIRU GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

THE MECHANICS OF ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

Academic writing has been of great essence to me so far in my Ph.D. journey with Euclid University. I appreciate the retrospective dive I made into the early days' archives of my first degree level when I took up the course Language and Communication Skills. In fact, I am very much excited that I have been given this opportunity to revise the nitty-gritty of the English Language which has imbibed in me better writing skills. I have attempted a Ph.D. program with at least two universities so far and I can confidently say that Euclid University's tuition stands tall. I appreciate the level of education I am receiving at this moment from EUCLID. This course is a good step towards a Ph.D. International Law and Treaty program I am pursuing in this prestigious institution of higher learning and it will go a long way to help in the writing of a thesis and other required courses.

2) ESSAY WRITING

The academic writing coursepack begins with the basics of essay writing. This part of the study manual addresses a lot of fundamental problems in writing. Sometimes it becomes difficult to transfer an idea about a given assignment unto a paper but the process to follow to write down an idea has been made easy in this Coursepack. The best practice when it comes to essay writing is to first and foremost, organize your ideas about the given topic. This is very important as it helps the writer to shape his or her ideas and plan how to go about the essay. It is essential not to procrastinate at this stage since it can delay the progress of the essay (EUCLID 2015, 2).

The second most important stage involved in essay writing is to research the given topic. Research is a very useful tool because it helps in organizing and shaping one's

thoughts on a given topic. It is very difficult for a good essay to be written without conducting research on the topic area because it helps gather useful information about a topic. Research is part of what I do in my day to day working life as a lecturer. I know how important it is and how impossible it will be to perform a task in the field of academia without first researching into the given task. I find the information in this coursepack very useful and relevant since it touches on all aspect of research that people in academia should know about. One point I find fascinating is indicated on page three of the coursepack which talks about notes taking during research. Sometimes one tends to just read without jotting down relevant information and their sources. Notes taking during reading helps to keep track of everything that one reads and also do proper referencing as well as avoid plagiarism.

After organizing your thoughts on the given topic and conducting the necessary research to gather relevant facts about the topic area, the next step is to do the write-up. In most cases, when people get to this stage they just move on straight with the essay writing. One thing I learned at the early stages of my education which I find repeating itself in the coursepack is to have a first draft of the essay. This helps in transferring every information gathered (i.e., your evidence) and knowledge gained unto a paper. After the first draft, editing is done to fine-tune it to get the final draft.

The last point I will like to talk about is the structure of the essay. The coursepack provides the structure to follow in writing essays (i.e., the introduction, the body, and the conclusion). This structure is a very good one as it corresponds to what I learned at the first degree level. Following the three-stage structure as provided in the coursepack is very essential to writing-up a good piece.

3) REFERENCING

In reading through the coursepack, I chanced on the two ways of referencing and which formats are acceptable by Euclid University for response papers and major papers. The two ways of referencing (i.e., in-text citation and list of works cited) have refreshed my knowledge. These two referencing styles are universal and reading through the coursepack made me remember the early days of my education when I learned about them. Nevertheless, I have learnt a lot more from the coursepack especially with regards to referencing styles. I knew about the American Psychological Association (APA) style and I had also heard about the Turabian referencing style but did not know much about it. In fact, going through this coursepack has taught me a lot about the Turabian referencing style and I am so much appreciative of the knowledge I have received. I now know that when it comes to an in-text citation, I have to reference by stating the surname and the page number of the book or article under review (EUCLID 2019, 16). I have learned a lot concerning quotations and paraphrasing especially, how to do short quotations and long quotations, how to do a better paraphrasing as well as the use of signal phrases in quotations and paraphrases.

I have sighted some academic and non-academic papers where the authors cited information which is common knowledge. To be honest, I did not see anything wrong with

it then but after going through this coursepack, I have been enlightened on the fact that citing common knowledge information is not a good practice. When writing a paper in an entirely new area where it is difficult to know which information is common knowledge and which is not, the coursepack has stated plainly that every information which is recurring in a particular area is considered common knowledge (EUCLID 2019, 31). This information provided in the coursepack is a very important message that will go a long way to help academics and non-academics in writing both academic and non-academic papers. The coursepack also gave very good detail about how to do a proper bibliography. There is a format for book referencing, online works referencing, etc. using the Turabian style of referencing. The formats are so clear and understandable that I think I am used to it already.

Footnote referencing is the other way of referencing aside in-text citation. It is important to double-check in Microsoft Word that footnote referencing has been selected and not endnote referencing. This piece of information provided in the coursepack is good since it serves as an alert to students, not to mistaken endnotes with footnotes. The rules of thumb for writing papers provided on page forty-three of the coursepack is also very helpful in coming up with a good academic paper.

4) CHICAGO STYLE AND USAGE

Chicago style of referencing is a widely accepted style of referencing used in academic writing. It helps in knowing how to do in-text citation, list of references as well as how to use punctuations in academic writing. The coursepack makes it clear that when it comes to the dictionary choice of Chicago style, Webster's Third New International Dictionary is preferred. Alternatively, Merriam-Webster's Collegiate Dictionary can also be used. In terms of abbreviations, I refreshed my knowledge on putting abbreviations such as e.g., i.e., and etc., in parenthesis. It is important to recognize that when it comes to geographical terms such as the name of countries, postal addresses, and prefixes to place, they should always be spelled out in the text.

In terms of capitalization, the coursepack has provided well-explained information on full caps, headings caps, and sentence caps. Under headings caps, the first and last words of all nouns, pronouns, adjectives, and subordinating conjunctions are capitalized (EUCLID 2015, 67). However, articles (e.g., a, an, the), prepositions (e.g., against, between, in, of), conjunctions (e.g., and, but, for, nor, or, so, yet) and initiatives (e.g., to) are not capitalized. When it comes to sentence cap, it is very useful to capitalize the first word of a title or heading, the first word after a colon and proper noun. It is important not to hyphenate compound nationalities and ethnicities.

5) CONCLUSION

Reading through period one coursepack has enriched my knowledge in academic writing so much so that some things I overlooked in the past will no longer be overlooked. Beginning from the techniques of essay writing, I have enriched my knowledge and learned

so many things I never knew. I do appreciate the information about the dos and the don'ts of in-text citation and list of works cited. I believe that now I can comfortably use the Chicago style of referencing; how to do proper abbreviation, acronyms, and even capitalization. This course pack has been very helpful to me and I am very grateful to Euclid University that even at this early stage of my Ph.D. in International Law and Treaty, I have gotten all this information at my disposal. I am very optimistic that the future with EUCLID looks very bright and I cannot wait to unravel all the good materials you have in stock for me.

REFERENCES

EUCLID. 2015. *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 1*. Washington DC: Euclid University Press. <https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-1>

Cleenerwerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.